

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

6 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 6, НОМЕР 4

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 6, ISSUE 4

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№4 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2023-4>

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ISSN: 2181-9297

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A HELPFUL TOOL OR MISLEADING CONCEPT?** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10157526>**ABSTRACT**

The purpose of this project was to discuss whether international language proficiency tests provoke and indicate literacy in the English language despite the high score, as the authors faced a little mismatch among some students who obtained one of those certificates.

As there were least researches on this point in Uzbekistan context, we will refer to the researches of other authors who had observed expanding circle students.

Keywords: The expanding circle, students, language proficiency certificates, language skills.

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университета имени А.И.Герцена в городе Ташкенте, Ташкент, Узбекистан**МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЕ ТЕСТЫ НА ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ВЛАДЕНИЯ ЯЗЫКОМ:
ПОЛЕЗНЫЙ ИНСТРУМЕНТ ИЛИ ВВОДЯЩАЯ В ЗАБЛУЖДЕНИЕ КОНЦЕПЦИЯ?****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Целью этого проекта было обсудить, провоцируют ли международные тесты на знание языка и указывают ли они на грамотность в английском языке, несмотря на высокий балл, поскольку авторы столкнулись с несколькими несоответствиями среди некоторых студентов, получивших один из этих сертификатов.

Поскольку в Узбекистане исследований по этому вопросу было меньше всего, мы обратимся к исследованиям других авторов, наблюдавших студентов с расширяющегося круга.

Ключевые слова: Расширяющийся круг, студенты, сертификаты о знании языка, языковые навыки.

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ХАЛҚАРО ТИЛ БИЛИШ ДАРАЖАСИНИ АНИҚЛАШ ТЕСТЛАРИ: ФОЙДАЛИ ВОСИТАМИ ЁКИ ЯНГЛИШ ТУШУНЧАМИ?

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу лойиҳанинг мақсади халқаро тилларни билиш тестлари юқори балл курсатгичига қарамай инглиз тили саводхонлигини кўрсатиш ёки курсатмаслигини муҳокама қилиш, чунки муаллифлар ушбу сертификатлардан бирини олган баъзи талабалар орасида номувофиқликка дуч келишди.

Ўзбекистонда бу борада энг кам тадқиқот олиб борилганлиги сабабли биз кенгайиб бораётган доира талабаларини кузатган бошқа муаллифларнинг тадқиқотларига мурожаат қиламиз.

Калит сўзлар: Кенгайиб бораётган доира, талабалар, тилни билиш сертификатлари, тил кўникмалари.

International tests like TOEFL and IELTS are specific to inner circle varieties of English (Davies et al., 2003, as cited in Kahn, 2009), and Ingram and Bayliss 2007; Thorpe et al. 2017 indicate that “IELTS adequately predicts test-takers’ abilities to function in an academic environment” (as cited in Pearson, 2019). However, sometimes the expanding circle students may struggle to comprehend and demonstrate an academic English despite high scores in them. And for this project we analyzed some researches conducted with students from expanding circle and would like to discuss another aspect of those tests: whether they indicate the literacy in English language as it is supposed to.

Nowadays, with the tendency to learn English whether to study abroad or local universities (Uzbekistan state universities accept language proficiency tests like IELTS and CEFR as placement tests) a lot of applicants rush to obtain one of those certificates. No doubt this is a positive tendency, however, it provokes another issue that affects students’ performance.

IELTS or CEFR tests are structured, thus, the candidates as well as the trainers who work on this field for a long time learned the ways or strategies of performing during the tests. And the candidates who obtained higher scores are often not those who know the English from the very basis but those who learned these structures very well. Kovalenko (2018) points out that though preparing for IELTS reading helps students to concentrate, control their anxiety and accelerate their decision-making skills while reading test texts they can hardly succeed in reading academic texts (as cited in Dang and Dang 2021). Other scholars, Sabet and Babaei (2017) found that listening to IELTS tasks and academic listening tasks were quite different in terms of pragmatic understanding, information literacy and skills integration (as cited in Dang and Dang 2021).

As for productive skills as writing this conception can be applied as well. Moore and Morton (1999) point out that the two tasks in IELTS were different in terms of genres, information source and others in comparison to university tasks with relevance to prior knowledge in former one (as cited in Lewthwaite, 2007). Merrylees (2003) indicates that the academic writing at the universities requires to use and evaluate carefully plentiful sources while in IELTS writing candidates can refer to newspaper or magazine sources (as cited in Lewthwaite, 2007). One more important aspect, the Speaking skill in IELTS is structured as well, and the test takers need to follow them using appropriate vocabulary to obtain good results. Islam et al (2022) mention that experienced trainers indicate that the candidates need to put efforts to build their vocabulary and work on reducing their anxiety while producing their speech (as cited in Luu Quy Khuong and Luu Ngoc Bao Trang, in 2022). Another issue is that the speaking topics are quite popular nowadays with answer samples that may give the advantage for some candidates. And again, this is not what is expected to produce in universities,

where students mainly need to think critically about the sources, summarize them and refer to them carefully.

Yang and Badger (2015) observed Chinese students who were studying in the UK and learned how IELTS preparation courses helped them in their studies. Students revealed that even though the preparation courses were helpful they were not much effective in “source use” and “extensive reading” (as cited in Dang and Dang 2021).

Yet another research was conducted with Vietnamese students who completed their 1st semester in the UK. Four Vietnamese students were interviewed about their IELTS preparation experience and their studies in the UK and their answers were the same, that critical thinking and synthesizing were essential skills in university assignments while they are not taught in the courses. And particularly, they have mentioned that there was less use of Writing Task 1, and even Task 2 was far more different than university tasks, where the requirement for vocabulary range and amount and quality was high. For instance, one student mentioned that it was hard to him to do his assignments because he had to read a lot of sources and write his assignments with related terminology with which he was unfamiliar while he could just write his already-existing knowledge in IELTS writing (Dang and Dang 2021).

Almost similar situation happens in Uzbekistan universities according to the reports of English teachers who indicate that though students were accepted to the universities with language certificates, some students struggle to perform in the target language. However, we must consider that local universities in Uzbekistan mainly focus on ESL, EFL and rarely ESP courses in their syllabus that much differs than academic requirements for the students who study in inner circle universities. And the latter one may cause even more misconfusion among the students who are totally ignorant of their field yet. In terms of ESL and EFL courses it is obvious that assignment may be different than in comparison to the inner circle courses, where students need to do a lot of extensive reading and analyze and synthesize to produce the work.

Discussion

Though these tests may be applied as placement tests in a number of universities, some students in expanding circles can rarely achieve the literacy that needed to incorporate in studies. We believe this mismatch may occur due to the language abilities and the skills of some students as certainly there are students who are sensitive enough to use the language correctly and aware of its rules. And another factor that may impact on them is their expectations about the university studies and specifications that those tests require. However, the question is unsolved whether language proficiency tests provoke the real literacy in target language and will they assist academic performance of the students. Undoubtedly, applicant “read” a lot of passages to pass the exam and mainly to learn to cope with the questions, however, it can hardly help them to READ the text and comprehend it especially under exam conditions. The same critics may be applied to other subskills.

Conclusion

Though these tests can assess the language skills of the applicants we need to consider that their score is not his/her final result, as different factors may cause that score. Anyway, the results of those tests must not confuse the candidates about their language skills and encourage them to learn further to master English.

As for language proficiency tests it would be better to keep them as the placement tests with minimum score that is required at universities, maybe 5.5 for BA, and minimum 6.5 for MA, without dividing to levels or band scores, indicating that applicant may cope with the academic tasks but needs further dedication. However, some tasks can be replaced by others, for instance Writing Task 1 to Article summary or so on.

And yet, we believe that this question needs further discussion and investigation to achieve perfection and reduce the mismatch that occurs in the tests and university classrooms.

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6 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

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ТОМ 6, НОМЕР 4

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 6, ISSUE 4

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
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